

Precision Farming with nano technology: A new era in agriculture

Mummasani Asritha^{1*}, G. Gowtham,² Kotresh D.J.³, Lokesh Singh Bohra⁴

¹Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Agronomy, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu – 641003,

²Ph.D. Scholar, Centre for Agricultural Nanotechnology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University - Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu – 641003, ³Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Agronomy, University of Agricultural Sciences, Bengaluru, Karnataka – 560065, ⁴PhD Scholar, Department of Agronomy, Govind Ballabh Pant University of Agriculture and Technology,

Pantnagar, U. S. Nagar, Uttarakhand-263145

Abstract

Precision instruments that maximize resources, boost yields, and encourage sustainability are being created with nanotechnology, transforming agriculture. It reduces waste and the impact on the environment by enabling targeted delivery of pesticides and fertilizers through nano-carriers when combined with technologies as GPS, GIS, and AI. Real-time crop health and ecological state monitoring is made possible by nano and bio-nanosensors, which promote efficiency of resources and well-informed decision-making. Furthermore, by increasing irrigation efficiency and soil water retention, nanomaterials help manage water resources. Nanotechnology promotes ecologically sound agriculture and international food safety by resolving issues like scarcity of resources and climate change. For wide adoption, future advances promise reduced chemical usage, waste reduction, and improved stakeholder collaboration.

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Introduction

To maximize agricultural productivity, farmers should adopt advanced technologies like nanotechnology that efficiently utilize resources, better farmer livelihoods, and foster an ecologically sustainable, pollution-free environment. Nanotechnology, a cutting-edge, interdisciplinary scientific approach, play a key important role in the development of innovative tools, devices, and systems at the nanometer scale (10^{-9} meters) (Auffan et al., 2009), offering novel applications in agriculture. Despite its many advantages-such as enhanced crop quality, environmental sustainability food security, safeguarding the environment, economic growth, profits, and productivity-precision agriculture is altering the world's agricultural landscape. Through the application of information technology, agricultural businesses can reduce inputs like fertilizer, insecticides, and herbicides while enhancing crop yields. Perhaps the most frequently utilized techniques for precision farming are satellite imagery, geographic information systems (GIS), and global positioning systems (GPS).

Further, it makes use of advances in technology in the form of nanosensors and nano-based smart delivery systems, which enable farmers manage crop with greater efficiency and generate better yields by enabling them use resources like water, fertilizer, and agrochemicals more effectively. Applications of nanotechnology in precision farming Agricultural efficiency and productivity are raised by variable rate technologies, precision farming, and nanotechnology. Precision agriculture uses variable rate technology (VRT) to apply fertilizers, insecticides, and herbicides effectively based on crop quality and soil type.

Applications of nanotechnology in precision farming

Variable rate technology, precision agriculture, and nanotechnology collaborate to enhance agricultural efficiency and productivity

Effective resource use enables farmers to increase growth and productivity while reducing expenditures and losses. By distributing inputs to selected regions, nanoparticles improve the performance of VRT (Sarauskis et al., 2022).

SMART DELIVERY SYSTEMS

Precise fertilizer, pesticide, and nutrient delivery is made possible by targeted nutrient and pesticide procedures employing nano-carriers, which greatly enhance farming methods. By using innovative agrochemical delivery techniques, nanohybrid structures—such as nano fertilizers—have earned a lot of attention for enhancing sustainable agricultural productivity while maintaining environmental quality. Because of their distinct physicochemical characteristics, nano fertilizers are more precise and effective than conventional chemical fertilizers since they can efficiently invade plant systems whether they are applied on leaves or delivered directly to the soil. Compared to traditional fertilizers, their ultra-small size results in a high surface area-to-volume ratio, that improves retention and absorption. Additionally, nano fertilizers retain more nutrients and release them gradually based on crop needs. Application of Fe-based nano fertilizers (Fe_3O_4) through foliar spraying increased physiological indicators by 33-66.7% and total protein content by 11.9-52.8% in *Catharanthus roseus* (Askary et al., 2017). In the pesticide industry, one of the most challenging areas is the nano formulation of traditional pesticides using metal nanoparticles or polymers. Nanoencapsulation of pesticides allows for controlled and sustained release of active ingredients by modifying the outer shell of the nano capsule. This method delivers a low dosage over an extended period while reducing the risk of excessive pesticide runoff (Agrawal and Rathore, 2014).

NANO AND BIO NANO SENSORS

By monitoring environmental factors and implementing targeted interventions, precision farming seeks to boost crop yields while reducing the need of fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides, and other inputs. Utilizing advanced technologies including computers, sensors, satellite positioning systems, and remote sensing instruments, farmers can measure and evaluate localized environmental conditions for optimal and ideal crop growth and precisely identify issues (Rai et al., 2012). Ultimately, precision farming, supported by smart sensors, enhances agricultural productivity by providing precise information, enabling farmers to make informed decisions. The e-Nose can assess rice aroma, enabling timely interventions to prevent aroma loss (Hu et al., 2020). Moreover, e-Noses are utilized to observe production processes and monitor pollutants in water or soil, plant diseases, and insect infestations. By using force curve acquisition, a functionalized atomic force microscopy tip equipped with the acetolactate synthase

enzyme identified the herbicide metsulfuron-methyl. Additionally, bio nanosensors allow for the quick identification and precise estimation of bacteria and viruses, increasing consumer food safety.

Modern instruments like nano sensors, which make it easier to detect heavy metals, pesticides, drug residues, foodborne pathogens, and harmful chemicals, are examples of how nanotechnology is advancing the advancement of diagnostic techniques. In order to improve crop management, experts are integrating biology, nanoscience, computing, and electronics to produce extremely sensitive nano sensors and nano-biosensors.

Precision agriculture is anticipated to be significantly impacted by nano sensors and nano-biosensors, which capture physiological data and transform them into easily identifiable, regularly spaced signals for improved monitoring and decision-making.

WATER MANAGEMENT

By optimizing irrigation systems, nanotechnology drastically reduces water consumption in agriculture, thereby mitigating the increasing worldwide water scarcity crisis. Nanomaterials regulate the flow and retention of soil water, increasing the effectiveness of irrigation systems. The weather, soil, and plant demands can be analyzed by artificial intelligence (AI) to optimize irrigation volumes and timings. For watering crops as efficiently, this AI method promotes water conservation.

SUMMARY

Owing to cutting-edge technologies like nano sensors, intelligent delivery systems, and fertilizers enriched with nanotechnology, farmers can now able to regulate resources with significant precision. This invention addresses major issues like climate change and sustainable farming while increasing crop yield and conserving resources like water and pesticides. By using nanotechnology in agriculture, we can improve crop health, reduce environmental damage, and increase agricultural productivity, all of which will contribute to the establishment of a more robust and sustainable global food system.

FUTURE PROSPECTS

The application of nanotechnology in agriculture has enormous potential to combat climate change and achieve sustainability. Chemicals and carriers at the nanoscale can improve the effectiveness of fertilizers and insecticides, lowering their dosage while preserving crop yields.

Precision agriculture may be further enhanced by nanosensor technology, which will help to increase yield, promote resource reuse, and minimize waste. To gain public acceptance and support for these innovations, it is essential to engage all stakeholders, including consumer groups and non-governmental organizations, in transparent discussions about the benefits and implications of this technology.

REFERENCES

- Agrawal, S., & Rathore, P. (2014). Nanotechnology pros and cons to agriculture: a review. *Int J Curr Microbiol App Sci*, 3(3), 43-55.
- Askary, M., Amirjani, M. R., & Saberi, T. (2017). Comparison of the effects of nano-iron fertilizer with iron-chelate on growth parameters and some biochemical properties of *Catharanthus roseus*. *Journal of Plant Nutrition*, 40(7), 974-982.
- Auffan, M., Rose, J., Bottero, J. Y., Lowry, G. V., Jolivet, J. P., & Wiesner, M. R. (2009). Towards a definition of inorganic nanoparticles from an environmental, health and safety perspective. *Nature nanotechnology*, 4(10), 634-641.
- Hu, X., Lu, L., Guo, Z., & Zhu, Z. (2020). Volatile compounds, affecting factors and evaluation methods for rice aroma: A review. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 97, 136-146.
- Rai, V., Acharya, S., & Dey, N. (2012). Implications of nanobiosensors in agriculture.
- Sarauskis, E., Kazlauskas, M., Naujokiene, V., Bručienė, I., Steponavicius, D., Romanekas, K., & Jasinskas, A. (2022). Variable rate seeding in precision agriculture: Recent advances and future perspectives. *Agriculture*, 12(2), 305.